

Why Special Relativity Rules Out Deterministic Conservation of Energy and Momentum

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. April 15, 2026

Conservation of energy and momentum are fundamental ideas of physics which appear in Newtonian mechanics and as such are considered to be deterministic. One may follow the center-of-masses of two particles $r_1(t)$, $r_2(t)$ up to an interaction and pinpoint energy and momentum at a specific x, t .

Special relativity is also deterministic (based on $x=vt$) and one would expect that conservation of energy and momentum should be enforced in a deterministic manner there as well. In every frame, one could write: Kronecker delta (E_1-E_2) Kronecker delta (p_1x-p_2x) ... Kronecker delta (p_1z-p_2z) . Such determinism would bypass quantum mechanics completely because quantum mechanics involves a non-deterministic approach to conservation of E, p .

We argue, however, that it is actually deterministic special relativity which gives rise to non-deterministic conservation of E, p for a specific reason. We suggest that in a rest frame, a particle with rest mass m_0 is associated with a running time t , but no notion of x space or momentum. One might be tempted to set $p=0$, but in principle we argue that there is no notion of momentum for a rest particle and no notion of space because it is simply sitting at one point. Momentum only arises if one views the particle at rest from a frame moving at $-v$, leading to $p = mv/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$. It is only in Newtonian mechanics that one introduces a priori a momentum which may then be applied in any frame. Such is not the case in special relativity.

If one takes this idea seriously, it has strong consequences because one cannot have a set of Kronecker deltas in each frame as listed above. One Kronecker delta in the rest frame $(m_0^1-m_2)$, would have to transform into Kronecker (E_1-E_2) Kronecker (p_1x-p_2x) for motion in the x direction alone. Mathematically a single Kronecker delta does not transform into two Kronecker deltas. One requires a mathematical function which describes energy conservation in the rest frame and then transforms naturally to describe both energy and momentum conservation in a moving frame.

Given that m_0cc and t are the only variables in the rest frame, we suggest a function based on the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$. If this is the case, then t and x must act as independent variables which at first seems like a problem because it is understood that $x=vt$. One may show, however, as we do in detail, that this invariant allows for fluctuations to t and x and so one may in fact create the function $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ (which is like a probability) and enforces non-deterministic conservation of energy and momentum. Non-deterministic conservation means that one must interact $\exp(-ip_1x)$ $\exp(ip_2x)$ over some space to obtain 0. Physically, this is linked to the notion that p hits occur probabilistically in space (2-slit experiment) and so this same probabilistic notion applies to conservation. Deterministic conservation at only one x, t is at odds with 2-slit interference which shows that one may interact probabilistically at two points in space. Thus, one must account for conservation of p at both.

Conservation of Energy and Momentum

Conservation of energy (elastic collisions) and conservation of momentum are two key ideas of Newtonian mechanics and are deterministic because one may follow two elastically colliding

particles through $x_1(t)$, $x_2(t)$. As a result, one may enforce conservation of energy (elastic collision) and momentum deterministically by using Kronecker delta functions:

$$\text{Kronecker delta}(E_1 - E_2) \text{ Product } i = 1, 3 \text{ Kronecker delta}(p_{1i} - p_{2i}) \quad ((1))$$

This seems to be what is done in Newtonian mechanics, and given that special relativity is formally deterministic, i.e. built on $x=vt$, it seems that ((1)) should also apply to special relativity. We argue, however, that it cannot.

The Issue of Momentum For a Particle with Rest Mass in Special Relativity

In Newtonian mechanics, one may assign an energy and momentum in every case. If a particle is at rest, its momentum is $mv = 0$ because momentum is defined a priori. We argue that momentum is not defined a priori in special relativity. In particular, if one starts with a particle with rest mass m_0 at rest at $x=0$, then there is no concept of space and no concept of momentum for this particle. This is the crux of our argument. The notion of momentum and space only appear when one views the particle from a frame moving at a constant $-v$. One may then find that:

$$m_0cc \text{ transforms into an } E = m_0cc/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \text{ and } p = mv/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad ((2))$$

It is special relativity which gives rise to the notions of E and p and in the rest frame, one cannot have any knowledge of p because it does not exist.

We argue that this idea has major consequences because it implies that one cannot use the Kronecker delta approach ((1)). In the rest frame, one has:

$$\text{Kronecker delta}(m_0c - m_0c) \quad ((3))$$

In a moving frame, one has ((1)), but a Kronecker delta does not naturally transform from ((3)) to ((1)). We thus argue against any possibility of a deterministic approach to conservation of energy and momentum. Instead one must have a math function which naturally transforms from conservation of m_0cc in the rest frame to conservation of E, p in the moving frame. We suggest that one consider the Lorentz invariant:

$$-m_0cct = -Et' + px' \quad ((4))$$

In the rest frame, one has m_0cc , while in the moving frame, E, p . Examining ((4)) and noting that E and p must be separately conserved suggests independence between x' and t' . In principle, however, special relativity is deterministic and based on:

$$x' = vt' \quad ((5))$$

This seems to pose a major problem.

Deterministic and Probabilistic dt,dx in Special Relativity

We wish to view ((4)) in terms of Newtonian mechanics in the $v \ll c$ limit. In such a case:

$$p = \text{Integral } dp = \text{Integral } F dt \quad ((6a))$$

$$\text{Kinetic energy} = \text{Integral } v dp = \text{Integral } F dx \quad ((6b))$$

If $E = m_0 c^2 + \text{kinetic energy}$, then:

$$-E dt + p dx = -m_0 c^2 dt - dt dx F + dx F dt = -m_0 c^2 dt \quad ((7))$$

Here dt and dx are deterministic values linked to $v = dx/dt$. As a result, one views the force F as acting on the center of mass and ((6a)) and ((6b)) as yielding the numerical values of E, p . This, however, does not mean that a moving particle renders E and p interactions at the center-of-mass point. We argue that special relativity in fact indicates that this is not necessarily the case as:

$$x, t \text{ and } x + \hbar/p, t + \hbar/E \text{ both give the same solution to } -Et + px \quad ((8))$$

\hbar/p and \hbar/E may be seen as fluctuations and so there is both a deterministic dx, dt and a probabilistic one \hbar/p and \hbar/E . The probabilistic solution is exactly what is required for x and t to be independent in $-Et + px$ for energy and momentum conservation. This allows one to create the probability:

$$\exp(-iEt + ipx) \quad ((9))$$

This quantum probability allows for E, p conservation, but not in a deterministic manner. In particular,

$$\text{Integral } dx \exp(-ip_1 x) \exp(ip_2 x) dx = 0 \text{ requires integrating over some region of space and not on a point } \quad ((10))$$

((10)) seems unusual given the notion of deterministic conservation of Newtonian mechanics, but seems to be consistent with the ideas of special relativity and quantum mechanics.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that it is deterministic special relativity, based on $x = vt$, which does not allow for a deterministic treatment of conservation of energy and momentum. If one could have such deterministic conservation, one would simply use Kronecker deltas for E, p_x, p_y, p_z in every frame. We argue that the fundamental problem is that it is special relativity which defines momentum. Thus, a particle at rest at $x=0$ has no notion of momentum or space. There is no concept of momentum in this frame and one can only impose a Kronecker delta for $m_0 c^2$, rest energy, i.e. Kronecker $(m_0 c^2 - m_0 v^2/c^2)$. The problem is that $m_0 c^2$ transforms into E and p , but a

Kronecker delta function does not mathematically transform. One requires a natural math transformation and we suggest that this does not occur for a deterministic function. Rather, we suggest that one consider the Lorentz invariant - $\text{mocct} = -Et' + px'$. Given that E and p must be separately conserved, this suggests that t' and x' be independent. This is a problem because special relativity is based on $x'/t' = v$. We show, however, that special relativity does allow for dt, dx fluctuation values which would make x' and t' independent. In other words, one must introduce probability for E and p interactions in t and x, which is not deterministic. One may then create the probability $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ to ensure a non-deterministic conservation, e.g. $\int dx \exp(-ip_1x) \exp(ip_2x)$. At first it may seem unusual that non-conservation requires integration in space to produce a 0 value, but we note that the results of 2-slit interference show that a p hit is not necessarily at one point and so one should not expect conservation of p at a single x or E at a single x.